

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21058735>

TRANSFORMATION OF FAKE NEWS AND INFORMATION ATTACKS IN THE CONDITIONS OF HYBRID WARFARE

Mamadaliyeva Zulfizar Yusufjon kizi

Independent researcher at UzDJTU

***Abstract.** This article provides a scientific and theoretical analysis of the role of fake news and information attacks in the modern media space as a means of hybrid warfare. As a result of the development of digital communication tools and social networks, the information space has become an important front in geopolitical competition. The study examines the mechanisms of spread of fake news, their impact on public consciousness, methods of information manipulation, and their functional role in the strategy of hybrid warfare. It also develops recommendations for ensuring information security and strengthening media literacy.*

***Keywords:** hybrid warfare, fake news, disinformation, information attacks, media space, information warfare, media literacy.*

Introduction. Currently, the topic of hybrid wars is being actively discussed in the media and various scientific forums. Experts give various, often mutually exclusive definitions of this phenomenon, which still lack terminological stability and clarity. However, the term hybrid war is currently manifested in a completely different form. That is, it appears in the form of information attacks, wars, conflicts and fake, trolling, chameleon, phishing news. Let us analyze how these terms and terms take their place in the media space and how they relate to hybrid war. Analysis of world experience shows that today direct aggression has ceased to be the only means of domination. In this regard, modern science is studying indirect forms of confrontation and paying special attention to information warfare.

The term “information war” is now more of a journalistic nature and has not yet been widely recognized. This is due to the fact that this concept actually hides, as well as disputes about the correctness and practical application of this term, which are usually referred to as information conflict or conflict of interests in the information sphere of social systems. Now, if we take the information conflict, those who say that these two concepts mean the same thing are absolutely mistaken. The concept of “information conflict” means a clash of opposing goals and interests, positions and

opinions, carried out with the help of information technologies. Participants in an information conflict can be subjects that have sources and means of information dissemination.

Experts from the Russian Foreign Ministry understand conflict in the modern information space as ¹"*a confrontation between states in the information system, causing damage to information systems, processes and sources, important structures, as well as undermining political, economic and social systems* . "

The article titled "Information Onslaught: Israel's Invisible War" states: *As a result of the Six-Day War between Syria, Jordan, Egypt and Israel in 1967, the West Bank, the Gaza Strip and East Jerusalem were occupied by Israeli soldiers. In the same year, the United Nations Security Council adopted Resolution 242, calling on Israel to immediately withdraw from the occupied territories. Israel has not complied with the demands of the Resolution. More than three million Palestinians have been living under illegal military occupation for almost half a century. We would like to tell you about one of the invisible wars that Israel is waging - the information offensive. The main topic of the article is how ²the US media is helping the Jewish state in this war , it is described as follows.*

According to Amnesty International, Israeli forces have routinely committed human rights violations in the occupied territories, including extrajudicial killings, torture and ill-treatment of prisoners, demolition of homes with people inside, blocking the passage of ambulances, denying humanitarian aid, and using Palestinian civilians as human barriers. These are called war crimes in international law. Gila Svirsky, leader of the Women for a Just Peace coalition in Israel, describes daily life in Palestine this way: " The oppression reaches such a level that when a state of emergency is declared, Palestinians cannot leave their homes for days , " she says. The reason is simple: the Israeli military does not want to see them on the streets. This means that they cannot buy food, send their children to school, or even cross the street to visit their neighbors . If they are sick, they cannot get medical care. So they cannot leave their homes to do any of the most important things they need to do . Living like this is a form of terror ³. "

According to American philosopher and political scientist Noam Chomsky , the Israeli occupation is the longest-running war crime in modern history: "The West Bank and the Gaza Strip are under military occupation. This is the longest-running occupation in modern history. This occupation is extremely harsh and brutal, and it is

¹Buksarin S.N. "UmnayaokhranailiKarfagendoljenbytrazrushen". URL: <http://avkrasn.ru/article>.

²Makarov V.E. "Political and social aspects of information security. Monograph". Taganrog: Izdatelstvo S.A. Stupina, 2015. C 9-8.

³JointPub 3-13 " InformationOperations ", DODUS , URL : http://www.c4i.org/jp_3_13.pdf

built on a foundation of violence from the beginning. Life has been reduced to a level that is unlivable for the population ¹. "

Based on the content of the article, in the modern world , military capabilities alone are insufficient to win a war. For this , the victorious side must also convince the international community under the auspices of the UN that it is waging a just war. Israel knows this well. For this purpose , Israel has, first of all, enlisted the support of the world leader, the father of democracy, and the standard - bearer of the information age, the United States . The American government has been Israel's closest friend since the emergence of the Jewish state . Since many resolutions adopted by the UN Security Council against Israel were vetoed by the United States, many crimes against humanity committed in Palestine still remain unpunished. However, it is worth noting that in order to win the war, Israel must rein in not only the US government, but also the independent media of this country. Because the most powerful and influential media in the world are located in the United States.

The Israeli-Palestinian conflict dominates the international news coverage in the US media. This news is the main source of information about the conflict for Americans. Therefore, it is important to examine what is being reported and question the facts. Today, it is difficult to find a person in the world who has not heard about the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. News about new clashes, new victims has become a common occurrence for many. No one asks why Palestinian youth hate Israel, why they always block the path of Israeli tanks with stones in their hands. Jewish human rights activist Gila Svirsky explains it this way: "We do not see the hardships that the Palestinians are going through. We cannot imagine how hard this occupation is for them. There is no pity, no sympathy. A pregnant woman dies at a checkpoint before she can reach the maternity hospital to give birth . If you do not see this, how can your heart ache?! How can you know that this occupation is wrong?! "According to American journalist Alice Solomon, the main reason for the problem is that journalists are not reporting what is happening to the world correctly . " That's the crux of the situation," he says ². "There's not enough reporting, we don't see the pictures . There's no analysis , there's not enough voice to describe the plight of Palestinians under occupation. It's gotten to the point where the world doesn't even know that the occupation is going on." **The relationship between the US media and Palestine** , news, especially television news, plays a key role in determining which events are more important and shaping our perception of these events. Israel uses the power of the American media to influence the minds of the American people. Robert Jensen, a

¹Savin L.V. Setevaya i setevaya voyna. Introduction and concept. M.: Evraziiskoe dvigienie, 2011. C -23.

²Rabin Havt, Ari, and Media Matters for America. Lies, Incorporated: The World of Post-Truth Politics. Anchor. 2016. pp. 37-49

professor of journalism at the University of Texas at Austin in the US, says that Israel is also fighting a second front against Palestine in America. “ Israel is, in effect, fighting a war on two fronts,” he says. The first is the ongoing military campaign against the Palestinian population in the occupied territories. The second is the PR campaign waged through the media to ensure continued US support for the Israeli occupation. Alon Pinkas, Israel’s Consul General in New York and PR coordinator, recently said: “We are at war with the Palestinians right now, and a successful PR campaign is one way to win this war ¹. ”

So, in addition to occupying the West Bank and Gaza, Israel is also trying to capture the American press through an attack of ideas . The history of the Israeli PR company dates back to the 1982 invasion of Lebanon. At that time, Israel was heavily criticized by the international community for its occupation of Lebanon, especially for the massacre of Palestinians in the Sabra and Shatila refugee camps. The thousands of civilians who died did not even break Israel's back. But the damage to its international "image" was a major problem that seriously worried the government. Robert Fisk, a correspondent for the British newspaper "The Independent", recalls those days: " They surrounded Beirut. In three months, they killed 17,500 people, almost all of them civilians. I saw thousands of bodies with my own eyes. Then the massacre began in the Sabra and Shatila camps. The world was shocked. The Israelis wondered what they had done wrong. Then, when they think about it, they could not have done good PR." ²This shows that the media's use of materials, i.e., the example of a fly, to the level of an elephant, in the vernacular, "making an elephant out of a fly", and attracting public opinion, certainly shows the high role of journalism, the Internet, visualization, and communication.

After the PR crisis in Lebanon, Israel decided to establish permanent research institutes to monitor how Americans think about the Middle East. In 1983, the Hasbara Project was launched to improve the US press. The goal was to train Israeli officials in the fields of communications and public relations. Special press secretaries were trained in Israeli consulates to increase the number of positive materials about Israel in the US media. One such press secretary said that he had breakfast, lunch and dinner every day, of course, with journalists, and during such meetings he discussed the content of the material to be broadcast or published with leading press and television producers. He calls this process “interaction.” According to journalist Alice Solomon, American journalists are fooled by this Israeli trick. “The Israeli press service regularly

¹Williamson Murray, Peter R. Mansoor. Hybrid Warfare: Fighting Complex Opponents from the Ancient World to the Present. Cambridge University Press. 2012. Page66.

²R. Ernest Dupuis , TrevorN . Dupuis . Vsemirnayaistoriyavoy (v 4- xtt .). Book 4 (1925-1997). SPb., M., "Polygon-AST". 1998. C.35-36

issues press releases, statements and information. They sit in a room in Jerusalem and write articles all day long without looking at the real situation or even trying to do so. The information provided by the Palestinian press service in this regard is almost useless. Because they cannot deliver ready-made article-level materials like the Israeli service,” says the American journalist . The news reported in the United States is influenced by a number of complex social relationships. News must pass through several ¹stages before it reaches the speaker . Before we can study how the Middle East conflict is covered by the American media, we need to understand how these relationships and processes work. One of the most important factors that filter the news is the business interests of the corporations that own the media. It is impossible not to emphasize this, of course. Such interests extend beyond the borders of the United States to the Middle East on the other side of the globe. The economic interests of media corporations prevail over everything, and they effectively use information wars and their various manifestations (fake, trolling, black PR, chameleon, phishing, etc.). Not only politicians, but also representatives of other spheres of activity are now considering information wars as an effective method to achieve their interests. The strategic importance of the Middle East is reflected in the media coverage of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. The third challenge is the PR campaign aimed at painting the public image of Israel. The Israeli government employs the largest private PR campaigns in America to implement its political and information programs. Israel's 9 consulates in the United States also involve journalists in this work. A number of large private companies owned by Christians and Jews support the organized actions against the media that are not friendly to Israel , and they constantly remind us of Israel's official position on this issue. One of such powerful organizations is AIPEC, the American-Israel Public Affairs Committee . This organization is the largest lobby of Israel in Washington. The way the Middle East conflict is reflected in the media is determined by the alliance of American economic and political circles with Israeli propaganda. It is unlikely that progressive organizations such as "Jews Against the Occupation" or "Americans for Peace", which are opposed to the policies of the Israeli government, will rise above such calls . Finally , if a piece of news critical of Israel leaks into the press, a number of pro-Israel groups that monitor the media begin to put pressure on journalists and the media. "There are right-wing organizations that are pro-Israel," says journalist Solomon. They call their work monitoring. I call their activities a threat to journalists. Under the pretext of impartial reporting, they actually want to produce material that is favorable to Israel .

¹R. Ernest Dupuis, Trevor N. Dupuis. *Vsemirnaya istoriya voyn* (v 4-x tt.). Book 4 (1925-1997). SPb., M., "Polygon-AST". 1998. C.54

Seth Ackerman, a representative of the US-based organization “Journalism for Justice and Integrity,” said that there are special groups whose job is only to write letters to the editor. “Their demand is that the news that criticizes Israel be changed or the people who wrote it be fired ¹.” In the article and the comments to it, we witnessed the games of information aggression being staged by major states on large platforms. “War” is an aggressive action directed against the population, as well as the enemy government, by peaceful and military means, in order to destabilize the internal and political situation and subjugate the will of the subject. Wars in the information space are characterized by the use of aggressive technologies. Thus, there are two types of conflicts in the field of information warfare and information confrontation, which are of opposite intensity. Another concept that is increasingly used in scientific discussions, but in some cases is misinterpreted, is “fourth generation wars.”

In the information space, experts from the RAND Corporation have developed a classification of four generations of wars:

- 1) first generation warfare using linear tactics;
- 2) second-generation wars were mainly positional in nature;
- 3) third-generation warfare, which is called mobile warfare;
- 4) Fourth generation warfare (hereinafter referred to as 4GW), where the primary goal is to morally subjugate the enemy ².

The fourth generation of wars includes the second generation of strategic information wars. They represent a fundamentally new type of strategic confrontation arising from the information revolution, which includes the information space and a number of other areas (economy, culture, etc.) within the possible spheres of confrontation. These wars imply a different approach: creating an atmosphere of moral and immorality, controlling the public consciousness and political orientation of the country's population; misinforming citizens about the activities of state bodies, undermining their authority, discrediting the enemy's government, etc. Fourth generation wars blur the line between civilian and professional soldiers. At the same time, war is never declared. Externally, there may even be very friendly relations between opponents. An aggressive state recruits, arms, trains and finances opposition non-state actors. Together they plan sabotage operations, both with the use of weapons (revolution) and without them, in actions, information attacks. These topics are widely supported by the media. In practice, after the development of 4GW (in Yugoslavia,

¹“ Information campaign : Israel 's vision ” . <https://initiative.org>

²Pozubenkov P.S., Pozubenkov S.P. Hybrid warfare in modern information spaces // Scientific and methodological electronic journal "Koncept". - 2016. C 106-107.

Egypt, Tunisia and other countries), in journalism this phenomenon is called “color revolutions” from a technological point of view ¹.

From the point of view of operational theory, 4GW is based on the theory of “controlled chaos”. Thus, 4GW is a war of effects. The one who can calculate the effects of higher orders, he can subdue the enemy. The 4GW strategy is based on the basic political principle that, if it is correctly applied, a strong political will can go beyond economic and military power. It belongs to the second generation of information wars, the so-called “color revolutions”, and their mechanisms are known. These wars are waged in stationary conditions, that is, when the conditions of the situation change slowly. In such wars, the one who surpasses the enemy in financial resources is considered the winner. It is also a third generation of information wars, which it defines as intelligent. In the 21st century, it is not necessary to resort to weapons, provoke military conflicts or resort to military aggression to solve geopolitical problems. Everything can be solved within the framework of information confrontation war. However, it should be noted that strategic information warfare has not only become a component of 4GW, but has also taken on the full form of hybrid warfare. The direct meaning of the word 4GW is a war strategy that involves the use of various weapons, military tactics, the destruction of military and civilian infrastructure and the infliction of large numbers of casualties, but it cannot be denied that the information and psychological components play an important role. In science, it is often allowed to equate information warfare with the American concept of unconventional warfare – unconventional warfare (UW). The concept of UW implies that the illegitimate enemy acts not independently, but with the direct tacit support of third states or organizations (non-state actors, non-governmental organizations, private armies, corporations, etc.). In other words, a particular state or organization finances an armed formation, trains its fighters, supplies weapons and ammunition, provides political support, and assists in other ways. It is worth noting that this concept was used in practice during the change of power in Iraq, Syria, and Libya.

Before the unconventional war in countries, information warfare began, in which elements of “controlled chaos” began to appear later. In addition, unconventional warfare was carried out in conjunction with information attacks to hide from the world community the reality of the war, the parties involved, and their true goals. However, we cannot equate information warfare with unconventional warfare. Usually, including in science and the public sphere, the term hybrid warfare is used as a synonym for unconventional warfare.

¹Gene Sharp. *The Politics of Nonviolent Action*. Boston, MA: Porter Sargent. 1973. 72 p.

One of the messages that has captured almost the entire audience in the information world is fake news. It is natural to ask what its current form is and how it benefits countries. Fake news is a false message that is deliberately spread in order to create a sensation. Fake news has the property of spreading quickly "like a virus", and its spreader does not have to be anonymous or pseudo-anonymous. It is easy to recognize that the message is fake and fight against it, says expert, Professor Andrey Manoylo. Fake news is primarily aimed at influencing the human psyche. That is, they encourage a person to act not with reason or logic, but under the influence of feelings and emotions, - says Manoylo¹. According to the expert, a frightening or sensational message poisons a person, and he is instantly filled with excitement and a desire to take some action. In most cases, fake news appears where an information vacuum has arisen. For example, if an important event or emergency occurs somewhere, people naturally have a need to learn more and more detailed information about it as quickly as possible.

In such a situation, when the government or the relevant organization delays the official publication of the necessary information, when press releases have to go through several instances before being published, an information vacuum appears. The void quickly begins to be filled with various fakes, rumors, and other false news. Even if a very complete official message is published after a few hours, no one will need it, because people will already be "fed up" with fakes. Therefore, the most effective way to combat fakes is to take the lead in the information diary, to be the first to convey the official point of view to the people. Nowadays, the question of who or what is the fake factory and its owners is on everyone's mind. It is worth giving the following example to this question. Recently, the Bellingcat news agency has been frequently mentioned. "Elliot Higgins", who is mentioned in the media as the organizer of the agency, has published a book. His partner "Hristo Grozev" or "Maurice Rakushisky" (both are the same person) has promised new revelations. The price of these revelations is already known - the authors of the fakes about the downed Boeing in Donbass, the chemical attack in Ghouta, the poisoning of the Skripals and Navalny never bothered to tell the truth. It is impossible to talk seriously about these fabrications - it can be called compromising for the genre of investigative journalism. But the history of the birth of the "Bellingcat" agency is quite interesting. I found it necessary to tell how this fake factory came into being. In early 2010, the head of American military intelligence in Afghanistan, Michael Flynn, published a very interesting report on the topic "How is intelligence configured?"²

¹Grigorev V.R. Informatsionnye virusy - new weapon of mass destruction // Informatsionnye voyny. Moskovskaya oblast: Yubileynaya. No. 3. 2008. C -11

²Fake - factory - and - its followers // <https://sputniknews-uz.com>.

Guerrilla warfare was making its demands, and the sophisticated intelligence structures were no longer able to meet them. Flynn, along with the authors, suggested that their colleagues collect information from anyone who wanted to provide information - be it local residents, journalists, women's organizations, UN employees, activists - in short, from everyone. The information was required to be collected not only on military topics, but on all the events taking place in the country. It was planned to reveal existing secrets along the way, to present the collected information to NATO allies, journalists, and everyone else. Properly formatted and transmitted information would become a weapon. It would show the local population how much the occupiers cared about them and turn the people away from the partisans. From an outside perspective, it would have presented a bright image of American democracy bringing law and order to the Middle East. Around the same time, British Army officer Bob Seely was serving in Afghanistan. They are mentioned in the British press as intelligence agents, but there is no solid evidence for this.

Conclusion. The world's information landscape has changed radically in the present era, and the processes of creating, processing and delivering information to the audience have accelerated to an unprecedented level. As a result of the development of digital technologies, Internet platforms and social networks, information exchange has reached a new level. At the same time, this process has also created problems related to the quality and reliability of information. In today's media space, fake information of various content, manipulative, misinterpreted and deliberately developed, is widely distributed. Especially due to the rapid circulation of information on social networks and the limited control mechanisms, false information has the opportunity to reach a large audience in a short time. This situation can lead to the formation of misconceptions in society, increased social distrust and artificial manipulation of public opinion. In this regard, fake news and information attacks are emerging as one of the important tools of modern hybrid warfare. Their main goal is not only to spread false information, but also to influence the minds of the audience, control decision-making processes and achieve dominance in the information field. In the fight against fake news, it is not enough to simply refute it. For this, it is important to develop fact-checking systems, increase the professional responsibility of journalists, widely promote media literacy and form critical thinking skills in the audience. Also, the introduction of mechanisms for detecting disinformation based on artificial intelligence and modern digital technologies is one of the urgent tasks of today.

USED REFERENCES LIST:

1. Buksarin S.N. Umnaya okhrana ili Carthagen doljen byt razrushen [Electronic resource]. - The mode is accessible: <http://avkrasn.ru/article>
2. Makarov V.E. Political and social aspects of information security: monograph. - Taganrog: Izdatelstvo S.A. Stupina, 2015. – S. 8–9.
3. Joint Publication 3-13. Information Operations. Department of Defense USA [Electronic resource]. – The mode is available at: http://www.c4i.org/jp3_13.pdf
4. Savin L.V. Setevaya i setevaya voyna. Introduction and concept. - Moscow: Evraziiskoe dvigienie, 2011. - S. 23.
5. Rabin Havt, Ari; Media Matters for America. Lies, Incorporated: The World of Post-Truth Politics. - Anchor, 2016. - Pp. 37–49.
6. Murray W., Mansoor PR Hybrid Warfare: Fighting Complex Opponents from the Ancient World to the Present. - Cambridge University Press, 2012. - P. 66.
7. Dupuis RE, Dupuis T.N. Vsemirnaya istoriya voyn: v 4-x tt. Kn. 4 (1925–1997). - SPb.; M.: Poligon-AST, 1998. - S. 35–36.
8. Dupuis RE, Dupuis T.N. Vsemirnaya istoriya voyn: v 4-x tt. Kn. 4 (1925–1997). - SPb.; M.: Poligon-AST, 1998. - S. 54.
9. Information Attack: Israel's Invisible War [Electronic resource]. – <https://tashabbus.org> (<https://tashabbus.org/>)
10. Pozubenkov P.S., Pozubenkov S.P. Hybrid warfare in modern information spaces // Scientific and methodological electronic journal "Koncept". - 2016. - S. 106–107.
11. Sharp G. The Politics of Nonviolent Action. – Boston, MA: Porter Sargent, 1973. – 72 p.
12. Grigorev V.R. Informatsionnye virusy – a new weapon of mass destruction // Informatsionnye voyny. – Moskovskaya oblast: Yubileynaya. - No. 3. - 2008. - S. 11.
13. The Fake Factory and Its Owners [Electronic resource]. – Access mode: <https://sputniknews-uz.com> (<https://sputniknews-uz.com/>)